

Unveiling the Unexpected: An Incidental Discovery of a Rare Breast Tumor on CTA - A Case Report

Mahvish Renzu MD^{1*}, Shrikanth Sampath MD², Vidhi Mehta MD², Shruthi Sekaran MD², Shanjeev Kumar Chitra MD², Adam Manzoor Qazi MD³

¹Department of Internal Medicine, Wayne State University School of Medicine/Trinity Health Oakland Hospital, Pontiac MI, USA

²Department of Internal Medicine, Mercy Catholic Medical Center/Trinity Health, Darby, PA, USA

³Department of Internal Medicine, Wayne State University School of Medicine/Detroit Medical Center, Detroit, MI, USA

Citation: Mahvish Renzu, Shrikanth Sampath, Vidhi Mehta, Shruthi Sekaran, Shanjeev Kumar Chitra, Adam Manzoor Qazi. Unveiling the Unexpected: An Incidental Discovery of a Rare Breast Tumor on CTA - A Case Report. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2024;3(2):1-3.

Received Date: 12 February, 2024; **Accepted Date:** 19 February, 2024; **Published Date:** 21 February, 2024

***Corresponding author:** Mahvish Renzu, Department of Internal Medicine, Wayne State University School of Medicine/Trinity Health Oakland Hospital, Pontiac MI, USA

Copyright: © Mahvish Renzu, Open Access 2024. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

INTRODUCTION

Myofibroblastoma (MFB) is a rare mesenchymal tumor that belongs to the family of "benign spindle cell tumors" of the mammary stroma.^[1] It accounts for less than 1% of all breast tumors.^[2] MFB usually affects older males and postmenopausal females. It is often asymptomatic and typically presents as a painless, slow-growing mass. Here, we report an incidental discovery of a breast mass on CTA coronary in an elderly patient presenting with chest pain, later confirmed as MFB on biopsy. Here, we emphasize the imaging appearance, diagnosis, and therapy of breast MFB to aid early diagnosis, as this entity is primarily an incidental discovery in males.

Keywords: Breast Tumor; Myofibroblastoma;

CASE PRESENTATION

A 75 yr-old male with a past medical history of hypertension, hyperlipidemia, and prior CVA, presented with complaints of exertional chest pain, fatigue and shortness of breath while eating. He had no significant family or social history. On presentation, his blood pressure was 164/97mmHg, and heart rate was 85 bpm. Physical examination was mostly benign without any skin changes, gynecomastia, nipple changes or retraction, and no supraclavicular or axillary lymphadenopathies. Labs were within normal limits and the EKG showed sinus rhythm. Due to his high risk, a CTA coronary was ordered to evaluate for coronary artery disease. Interestingly, the CTA coronary revealed a right lower breast lump measuring 20 x 14 mm that was potentially malignant (**Figure A**). USG-guided biopsies were taken from the right breast mass, confirming the diagnosis of MFB on the pathological exam (**Figure B**).

The patient underwent a successful wide local excision of the right breast mass with margins and the repeat histopathology was consistent with myofibroblastoma.

(A) Axial computed tomography of chest showing soft tissue lesion

(B) Ultrasound of the right breast showing soft tissue lesion.

DISCUSSION

In the last few decades, Cardiac imaging has found itself a spotlight benefiting from massive advancements and increased usage. Improvement in cardiac MRI, CT and advanced qecho now allows detailed visualization. These non-invasive diagnostics have become an essential tool in Cardiovascular prevention.^[3] Additionally, an aging population, screening programs and research lead to increased utilization leading to increased incidentalomas. While it can often lead to early detection, false positives can lead to unnecessary intervention. When the physician

ponders “Should I intervene?” they must find a balance between the boon of early diagnosis and the bane of overtreatment.

REFERENCES

1. McMenamin M, Fletcher CD. Mammary-type myofibroblastoma of soft tissue: a tumor closely related to spindle cell lipoma. Am J Surg Pathol. 2001;25(8):1022-9.
2. Wordekemper J, Pierce R, Christopher TD. Male mammary myofibroblastoma. Annals of Internal Medicine: Clinical Cases. 2022;1(9).
3. Daubert MA, Tailor TD, James O, Shaw LJ, Douglas PS, Koweek LMH. Multimodality cardiac imaging in the 21st century: evolution, advances and future opportunities for innovation. Br J Radiol. 2021; 94(1117): 20200780.